

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF NET NEUTRALITY IN COLOMBIA, INDIA, AND THE UNITED STATES

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1.1 Introduction

The term “net neutrality” was coined as an extension of the concept of a “common carrier” by Tim Wu, a professor of Columbia University (Mukerjee, 2016). The principle that internet service providers (ISPs) must treat all data on the internet equally without discrimination, net neutrality has become a focal point of policy discussions globally (El-Bawab, 2021). In recent years, this subject has been a major source of debate in between content providers, and ISPs with each side trying to exploit their assets and expand their profit and influence (Alharbi et al., 2020). While the internet has been a catalyst for democratizing access to information and fostering global communication (Salerno & Rigney, 2024), challenges arise when accessibility of the internet is controlled by certain people who wield the power to prioritize or throttle certain content for commercial or political reasons. According to (Kumar et al., n.d.), this becomes the loss of mankind’s freedom of expression, livelihood and definitely the loss of great human invention. Therefore, the legal and regulatory frameworks governing net neutrality play a crucial role in safeguarding an open and equitable internet.

The legal state of net neutrality varies significantly across countries, shaped by local political, economic, and societal factors. While some nations have adopted robust protections to ensure an open internet, others have allowed more leeway for ISPs to prioritize certain traffic (El-Bawab, 2021; Kumar et al., n.d.). In the United States, for example, policies regarding Net Neutrality have fluctuated under different administrations (Stocker et al., 2020). In India, the regulatory environment has leaned toward strong protections for net neutrality, viewing it as essential for preserving democratic values in an increasingly digital society (Kumar et al., n.d.). Colombia, on the other hand, faces unique challenges in implementing net neutrality laws that balance digital inclusion with economic growth.

By examining these countries through the lens of freedom of expression and digital inclusion, this paper aims to contribute to the broader discussion of how internet governance can be shaped to ensure fair and equal access to information in the digital age.

1.2 Scope of Work:

Given the limitations of the paper, our research will only touch on the relationship between net neutrality, freedom of expression, and the digital divide in three countries. The choice of countries was arbitrary, based on the origins of some of the researchers. It is acknowledged that economic and corporate considerations are relevant to the core concepts of net neutrality; however, due to space limitations, this paper serves as a brief overview of the state of net neutrality in three different countries, analyzing only some of the issues that impact access to the internet.

1.3 Research Questions:

1. What is the legal state of Net Neutrality in Colombia, India, and the United States?
2. Which societal factors, including digital inclusion and freedom of expression, play a role in the development of net neutrality policies in each context?
3. What are the consequences of different Net Neutrality policies for internet users, ISPs, and content providers, in terms of access, competition, and digital inclusion?

II. Literature review and theoretical framework:

1. Net Neutrality and Freedom of Expression

The fundamental concept of freedom of expression is enshrined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UN, 1948), which asserts that individuals possess the right to seek, receive, and disseminate information. In its most fundamental sense, the concept of net neutrality is inextricably linked to the principle of freedom of expression. It is a regulatory framework that ensures that internet service providers treat all data transfer on the internet in an equal and impartial manner, irrespective of the source, user, content, platform, or application involved. This guarantees that users have access to all available information online and the right to seek, receive, and impart said information without being subjected to filtering or biases (Phippen, 2024). Consequently, net neutrality serves as the defense line for freedom of expression by upholding a neutral and accessible internet. It guarantees that all users, regardless of their background or resources, can access information and express themselves without external interference. The academic debate on the interdisciplinary field of freedom of expression also extends to the field of market competition and media concentration. This raises questions about the paradoxical nature of the current Internet neutrality regulation, which has the habit of sheltering Big Tech companies while allowing them to exclude smaller firms and their contents from the digital communication environment (Comeig et al., 2022). The present study will, however, limit its scope to an examination of the social sciences aspect of the debate, specifically the state of the legal framework on net neutrality as it applies to internet service providers (ISPs), together with an analysis of the government's policies and their impact on users and society.

Several legal frameworks around the globe have established a connection between net neutrality and the right to freedom of expression. The most notable of these was the First Amendment to the Constitution of the United States of America, which enshrined the right to freedom of speech. Another was a resolution from the Council of Europe, which called for all member states to develop national laws to protect freedom of expression by guaranteeing the net neutrality principle (CoE, 2016). Additionally, several pieces of literature have discussed the significance of net neutrality in upholding the First Amendment in the United States (Day, 2021; Nunziato, 2008). In the context of the United States, the First Amendment was directly violated when several network providers attempted to restrict access to anti-war and anti-George Bush websites during the Iraq War (Nunziato, 2008).

This prompted lawmakers to take action against the ISPs, requiring them to adhere to the First Amendment obligations.

The principle of net neutrality generally prohibits Internet Service Providers (ISPs) from blocking or throttling access to websites that express discontent or controversial viewpoints, effectively functioning as a censorship tool. This signifies that users can access any content or information presented online without any restrictions imposed by ISPs. This also empowers marginalized demographics and smaller businesses to have the same access to online assets and information as other large, established entities, thus reinforcing freedom of expression for all.

The debate around this concept has evolved continuously since its inception, with scholars proposing new concepts to illustrate the state of neutrality in the modern Internet ecosystem. These include "platform neutrality" (Krämer & Schnurr, 2018) and "data neutrality" (Easley et al., 2018). The advent of platform megacorporations and big data has rendered the previous terminology, such as ISPs, increasingly irrelevant in the digital economy and society. Contemporary terms, such as digital platform providers or data service providers (Hildebrandt & Wiewiorra, 2024), are emerging to replace them. It is thus evident that the concept of net neutrality must evolve beyond the traditional paradigm between ISPs, users, and governance. Despite the absence of a definitive definition of net neutrality, the academic discourse surrounding its implications for freedom of speech has reached a consensus on the necessity of establishing a set of principles that guarantee non-discriminatory treatment by pivotal actors in the Internet ecosystem concerning the regulation of digital communication bottlenecks, irrespective of whether these relate to bandwidth, access to platform functionalities, or big data. (Hildebrandt & Wiewiorra, 2024).

2. Net Neutrality and Digital Divide

Another societal impact of net neutrality is the widening of the digital divide. The digital divide theory refers to the gap between those who have access to information and communication technologies (ICTs) and those who do not (Van Dijk, 2017). This gap is based on a number of factors, including socioeconomic status, geographical location, and demographic characteristics. Scholars have posited that a lack of internet access serves to exacerbate marginalization in information-based societies (Ragnedda, 2017) and reflects broader socioeconomic inequalities (Nulens, 2003). The digital divide can be conceptualized in three distinct levels. The initial level of the digital divide pertains to the physical accessibility of technology, which is influenced by factors such as income, education, and race (Van Dijk, 2017). The second level of the digital divide pertains to digital skills, usage, and the ability to derive benefits from technology. Despite access, inequalities persist due to varying competencies (Ragnedda, 2017). The third level of analysis focuses on the societal and cultural benefits of internet use. Ragnedda (2017) posits that factors such as quality, autonomy, and support networks exert an influence on these benefits.

Internet access has the potential to enhance opportunities, yet it frequently serves to reinforce existing socio-economic cycles. The concept of net neutrality posits that the Internet should be accessible to all in a fair and equitable manner. This can be translated directly to digital equity, which is the ability of all individuals, regardless of their

socioeconomic background, race, gender, or other characteristics, to access high-speed, reliable, and comprehensive content available on the Internet. In the absence of these conditions, ISPs may simply throttle down the speed of service to certain websites and restrict users' access to competitor services for their own benefit. In conclusion, net neutrality can be seen as a means of levelling the playing field and empowering underserved communities to fully participate in the digital network and make the most of the resources available online. This, in turn, has the potential to close all three levels of the digital divide (CTN, 2023).

In practice, the implementation of these concepts has been demonstrated to present a more intricate set of challenges. The majority of scholarship discussions on the impact of net neutrality on the digital divide have highlighted the challenging dilemma that arises when the costs associated with an unrestricted, neutral Internet connection make it unaffordable for the majority of low-income users. The dilemma arises when policies designed to uphold net neutrality may inadvertently impede investments in accessible, affordable Internet for rural populations or citizens from developing countries. This is a concern highlighted by scholars such as Sambuli (2016) and Longe (2020). This indicates that net neutrality may have adverse effects on at least the initial level, if not all three levels, of the digital divide. It may deter private investment in digital infrastructure and services for underserved communities, as it conflicts with their business interests (Hildebrandt & Wiewiorra, 2024).

A prevalent strategy employed by internet service providers (ISPs) in low-income countries is zero-rating, which allows users to access content from prominent content providers at no cost on their devices (typically mobile phones). However, users must pay an additional fee if they wish to access services from competitors (Malcolm, 2014). This practice is particularly prevalent among Facebook users in developing countries. When coupled with the growing media consolidation of major technology companies, users from lower socioeconomic backgrounds are at risk of exploitation by these entities, as they restrict users from comprehensive access to all internet services. Nevertheless, if net neutrality regulations are to be strictly enforced, the investment in digital infrastructure may be adversely affected, as evidenced by case studies in rural communities in the United States (Longe, 2020; Merod, 2024).

III. Methods

This study employs a comparative legal and socio-political analysis to assess net neutrality regulations in Colombia, India, and the United States. The qualitative study design was chosen because of its ability to provide a deep, nuanced understanding of complicated legal frameworks and sociocultural elements that influence internet governance. Given the differences in political, economic, and social situations across the three countries selected, this methodology allows for a thorough evaluation of net neutrality policies and their impact on digital inclusion and freedom of expression.

The primary units of analysis are the legal frameworks governing net neutrality, societal factors like digital inclusion and freedom of expression influencing policy development, and real-world case studies demonstrating the implementation of these laws. Legal documents such as U.S. Federal Communications Commission (FCC) rulings, India's TRAI guidelines,

and Colombia's Law 1450 will be reviewed, alongside case studies such as the Facebook Free Basics debate in India and legal challenges in the United States.

The theoretical framework links the legal analysis of net neutrality to its broader societal consequences, especially because of the internet's role in promoting democratic participation and equitable access to information ([Phillips, 2024](#)).

Colombia, India, and the United States were chosen for this study due to their diverse approaches to net neutrality, which reflect distinct political, economic, and cultural contexts. The United States has a free-market, deregulated model ([Stocker et al., 2020](#)); India has strong legal protections for net neutrality ([TRAI, 2017](#)); and Colombia faces issues in reconciling digital inclusion with market-driven factors ([Triviño et al., 2023](#)).

The strength of this methodology is in its ability to combine legal analysis with societal impacts, offering a holistic understanding of how net neutrality policies shape access to information. However, the limitation of this study is that the focus on qualitative data may not fully capture the quantitative impact of these policies on internet users. If time allowed, conducting surveys or user-centric data could complement the qualitative study by providing insights into the lived experiences of internet users in all three countries.

IV. Case study

United States

Net neutrality discussions emerged in the US from landmark cases *Madison v. FCC* (2005) and *Comcast v. FCC* (2010), which revealed significant gaps in internet service regulation. These cases highlighted the need for clearer oversight of blocking practices and service provision ([CRC, 2022](#)).

The policy landscape has seen dramatic, back and forth shifts. During Trump's presidency, net neutrality protections were removed. While the FCC restored these protections in April 2024, establishing new standards for broadband reliability and consumer protection, the Sixth Circuit Court blocked these rules in August 2024. This decision favored broadband providers, citing their likely success in legal challenges due to their economic influence ([Shepardson, 2024](#)). The future of net neutrality remains uncertain, particularly given the potential impact of Trump's re-election ([Martin et. al, 2024](#)).

A fundamental challenge lies in the lack of consensus on net neutrality's definition, which hampers public understanding. Internet service providers narrowly define its absence as "blocking, throttling, and paid prioritization" - practices they claim to avoid. This ambiguous definition allows providers significant latitude in interpreting and implementing their own rules ([Feiner, 2024](#)).

The debate is heavily influenced by economic factors. In the United States' economically liberal, free-market environment, major ISPs like Verizon and AT&T invest substantially more in lobbying against net neutrality compared to supporters like Google and Microsoft ([Drutman & Furnas, 2021](#)).

The digital divide adds another layer of complexity. While organizations like Americans for Prosperity oppose net neutrality, arguing it creates financial burdens and obstacles to closing the digital divide (Czerniawski, 2023), evidence suggests the opposite. Without net neutrality protections, the digital divide risks widening as premium pricing excludes low-income citizens and racial minorities (Merod, 2024).

The 2018 repeal's impact was initially subtle, as companies maintained their best behavior. However, providers gradually implemented practices like throttling (intentionally slowing internet speeds) and zero-rating plans (excluding certain apps from data charges), demonstrating the real-world consequences of reduced protections (Bowman, 2024).

Colombia

In the case of Colombian Law, there are some laws and resolutions that try to regulate net neutrality. Law 1450 of 2011, in Article 56, declares that ISPs may not block, interfere, discriminate or restrict the right to use, send or receive Internet access or connectivity. However, in the first paragraph it states that ISPs "may make offers according to the needs of market segments or their users, according to their usage and consumption profiles, which shall not be understood as discrimination" (Congress of the Republic of Colombia, 2011). From the same year, Resolution CRC 3502 established the principles of user choice, non-discrimination of content, transparency and traffic management information (CRC, 2022).

In 2021, El Veinte, a civil society organization, directly challenged the constitutionality of the first paragraph of Article 56 of Law 1450 of 2011. The NGO asserts that this segment is discriminatory and violates articles 13, 15, 20, 75, 83, and 333 of the Political Constitution, as well as articles 11 and 13 of the American Convention, and articles 17 and 19 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (Corte Constitucional, 2021).

Societal factors significantly shape the practice of net neutrality policy in Colombia, influenced by challenges to digital inclusion and freedom of expression. The digital divide is wide, with 20% of the population lacking internet access and rural areas faring worse, with 68% of households lacking connectivity (Botero, 2023; DANE, 2023). Socio-economic disparities extend to internet speed, with lower income groups receiving speeds of 26.1-49.3 Mbps, compared to 148.6-142.9 Mbps for the wealthiest (MinTIC, 2022). Market concentration exacerbates access problems; two providers control 60% of fixed internet, and one private company dominates 50% of mobile connections (MinTIC, 2022).

In 2015, Colombia became the first country in Latin America to use Facebook's Internet.org, an initiative that reportedly provides free access to a dozen websites online. During the launch event, Zuckerberg said "By giving people these basic tools for free, you're creating an equal playing field" (Murphy & Acosta, 2015). This initiative was seen as a threat to net neutrality by some civil society organizations due to limited access, risk of discrimination, and consequences for civic participation in the post-conflict period (DW Academy, 2019).

Zero-rating services, while socially acceptable because they could bring internet access to the poorest and most vulnerable, pose a challenge to net neutrality. Threats to freedom of expression, including the killing of journalists and increasing stigmatization, further hinder political control (FLIP, n.d.). Limitations to media content in underserved areas, where half of the communities have no local outlets, leave residents uninformed about critical local issues (FLIP, 2019).

Colombia's current law fails to fully uphold net neutrality, leading to several consequences and some paradoxes. Limited internet packages offered by ISPs reduce users' autonomy, infringing on their rights to information and civic participation but at the same time is seen as the only option to bring internet access to some regions. This economic-based restriction on access constitutes discrimination, as affordable plans for diverse socioeconomic groups are lacking (Circuito Digital, 2024).

The legal framework favors zero-rating services and restricted data plans, which benefit platforms like WhatsApp, Facebook, and YouTube. These practices compromise freedom of expression and information access. Furthermore, the absence of clear net neutrality guidelines fosters artificial scarcity, reduces service quality and competition, and limits innovation. This ambiguous framework ultimately stifles technological and economic growth in Colombia.

India

In March 2015, the Telecom Regulatory Authority of India (TRAI) ignited a nationwide debate with a consultation paper addressing net neutrality. The controversy escalated when Airtel Zero and Facebook's Free Basics faced criticism in April for selectively offering free internet services. As Mukerjee (2016) emphasizes, these initiatives risked creating a "walled garden" where select companies controlled access, undermining the open and equal nature of the internet.

Facebook's Free Basics, initially framed as a tool to bridge the digital divide, quickly became a flashpoint. Critics contended that limiting access to certain services enabled Facebook to monopolize internet access in developing regions (Prasad, 2020). This sparked the rise of the Save The Internet Coalition, a grassroots movement that harnessed public sentiment. By leveraging social media and uniting diverse stakeholders—including startups, activists, and cultural influencers like All India Bakchod—the coalition mobilized over one million emails urging TRAI to enforce net neutrality protections (Save the Internet Coalition, 2015a).

The public outcry culminated in February 2016 when TRAI issued a historic ruling banning differential pricing for data services, effectively halting Free Basics and similar programs. This decision was solidified in July 2018, as the Department of Telecommunications (DoT) adopted comprehensive net neutrality regulations. These rules prohibited ISPs from practices such as blocking, throttling, and prioritization, positioning India among global leaders in net neutrality enforcement (Department of Telecommunications, n.d.).

The movement's success reflected the convergence of societal advocacy and political accountability. Grassroots campaigns fostered a broad consensus, transcending urban and rural divides. Social media served as a key mobilization tool, amplifying voices from across India. Startups and businesses joined the call, emphasizing the need for a fair and innovative digital ecosystem. Policymakers, responding to this groundswell, aligned legal reforms with the practical demands of India's digital economy (Subramanian, 2023).

The impact of these measures is profound. Net neutrality safeguards ensure affordable, unrestricted access for users, bridging the urban-rural digital divide. ISPs are subject to rigorous regulations, fostering fair competition while preventing exploitative practices (Cheng et al., 2011). Moreover, startups and smaller content providers gain a level playing field, enabling them to thrive without the threat of exclusion by dominant corporations (Kumar, 2016).

V. Discussion

In all three countries, the net neutrality conversation finds a common starting point in The net neutrality debates in the United States, Colombia, and India share common themes, particularly concerning zero-rating services, the influence of telecom companies, and the role of civil society. However, the context and outcomes in each country vary significantly, shaped by unique challenges of digital access, public awareness, and regulatory frameworks. Below, we explore these themes and draw comparisons across the three countries.

1. Zero-Rating Services and Market Dynamics

Zero-rating, where ISPs provide free access to specific services while excluding others, has been a central issue in the net neutrality debates in all three countries. In the U.S., Facebook and Wikipedia's Free Basics sparked significant discussions about how such practices could undermine competition and create monopolistic conditions. Facebook Zero, in particular, was criticized for creating a "walled garden" effect, where users gained access only to Facebook and a limited set of websites (Mukerjee, 2016). In India, Facebook's Free Basics and Airtel Zero faced widespread opposition in 2015. Both were seen as attempts to create a controlled internet environment that limited access to certain services, undermining the open and equal nature of the internet. The backlash in India was so strong that it led to the banning of such zero-rating practices in 2016 (Save the Internet Coalition, 2015). In Colombia, Facebook's Internet.org was launched in 2015 to bring internet access to underserved areas. While this was seen as a tool to reduce the digital divide (Murphy & Acosta, 2015), it also raised concerns about monopolistic behavior, especially since Facebook became synonymous with the internet for many users.

2. Telecom Companies' Re-definition of Net Neutrality

Telecom companies have played a crucial role in shaping the discourse around net neutrality, often attempting to redefine it to support their business interests. In the U.S., major ISPs

like Verizon, Comcast, and AT&T have argued that net neutrality regulations hinder investment and innovation. They have sought to reframe net neutrality as regulatory overreach, claiming that allowing for "reasonable" data prioritization would improve network management and user experience, particularly for services requiring higher bandwidth. In Colombia, the telecom sector has not been as vocal about redefining net neutrality, but the existing regulatory framework allows some zero-rating services, creating a paradox where limited internet packages may be the only viable option for underserved areas, despite undermining the principles of net neutrality. In India, telecom companies like Airtel and Reliance tried to justify zero-rating services as necessary for business growth and network optimization. However, the public backlash against Facebook's Free Basics and Airtel Zero led to strong net neutrality protections in India, banning such practices in 2016.

3. Civil Society Participation and Advocacy

India's SaveTheInternet movement stands out as one of the most successful examples of grassroots activism. The movement, which was supported by over a million online petitions, successfully halted Facebook's Free Basics and Airtel Zero, resulting in the adoption of strong net neutrality regulations in 2018 (Subramanian, 2023). Civil society has played a critical role in the net neutrality debates, particularly in the U.S. and India, where high levels of internet access have facilitated large-scale activism. In contrast, Colombia's activism has been limited, largely due to the country's significant digital divide. With 20% of the population still lacking internet access, many citizens are unaware of or unable to engage in the net neutrality debate (Botero, 2023). This disparity underscores how digital access directly affects the ability of civil society to influence policy. In the U.S., organizations like Free Press and the Electronic Frontier Foundation (EFF) mobilized online campaigns, generating public pressure on the Federal Communications Commission (FCC). These efforts were instrumental in reinstating net neutrality protections in 2021, only to face legal setbacks shortly after (Shepardson, 2024).

4. Challenges and Impact on Digital Access

In Colombia, challenges stem from the lack of clear net neutrality guidelines, which have allowed zero-rating services to thrive despite nominal legal protections. This regulatory ambiguity has led to paradoxical situations where limited internet plans are seen as the only option in underserved areas but undermine net neutrality principles (Circuito Digital, 2024). The challenges each country faces in enforcing net neutrality laws are deeply influenced by the level of digital access and political will to protect open internet principles. In the U.S., the repeal of net neutrality protections under the Trump administration and subsequent legal battles have created uncertainty. The FCC's attempt to restore protections in 2024 was blocked by courts, leaving the future of net neutrality unresolved (Shepardson, 2024). In contrast, India's net neutrality laws have had a significant positive impact, ensuring equitable access across the country. However, challenges persist, particularly in rural areas, where internet access remains limited and dominated by large telecom providers (Cheng et al., 2011).

Aspect	United States	Colombia	India
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What Led to the Law	Landmark cases (Madison v. FCC, 2005, Comcast v. FCC, 2010) revealed gaps in internet service regulation.	Law 1450 of 2011 laid the foundation; Civil society challenged discriminatory practices (2021).	TRAI's 2015 consultation sparked nationwide debate, particularly against Airtel Zero and Free Basics (Facebook).
Timeline of the Law	Net neutrality rules were introduced in 2015, repealed in 2017, and partially restored in 2024.	Law 1450 (2011); challenges in 2021 led to further discussion.	Net neutrality rules were adopted in 2016, with comprehensive regulations established in 2018.
Challenges	Ambiguous definitions of net neutrality, economic influence of ISPs, and political shifts (Trump presidency).	Digital divide, economic restrictions, and market concentration; lack of clear net neutrality guidelines.	Opposition from large corporations (Facebook's Free Basics); balancing digital inclusion with fairness.
Meaning of Net Neutrality	Focus on "blocking, throttling, and paid prioritization"; contested by ISPs as regulatory overreach.	Broad, but includes exceptions for market-driven services, leading to ambiguity and challenges in implementation.	Defined as a ban on differential pricing and practices that restrict open access to the internet.
Impact	Repeal led to throttling and zero-rating practices, widening the digital divide.	Zero-rating practices (e.g., Facebook's Internet.org) compromised net neutrality, limiting access and information.	Banned differential pricing, promoting fair competition and expanding internet access across diverse regions.
Civil Society	Significant online campaigns (e.g.,	El Veinte NGO challenged	SaveTheInternet Coalition mobilized

Participation	Free Press, EFF) mobilized public opinion against ISPs.	discriminatory practices in law; civil society organizations criticized zero-rating.	millions through social media, uniting a diverse group of activists and businesses.
Current Situation	Net neutrality remains in legal limbo, with potential future changes depending on legal challenges and political shifts.	Legal framework still allows for discriminatory practices; internet access remains uneven.	Strong net neutrality protections, fostering competition and ensuring equal internet access.

Table 1.1

Future Direction of Research

Future research on net neutrality should broaden its scope to encompass a wider range of factors that were not included in this paper.

First and foremost, regarding methodology, the research would greatly benefit from more quantitative data, which could be collected through surveys or statistical analysis, for example, to measure the digital divide level within underserved communities that are under the protection or without the protection of net neutrality, or to measure the awareness level on the topic of net neutrality itself.

Secondly, the role of media concentration and the dominance of large tech companies in shaping the digital landscape needs further scrutiny, examining their influence on policy debates, user behavior, and the overall health of the internet ecosystem. In the ever-changing digital economy paradigm, where mega-corporations are blurring the lines between ICPs and ISPs with bigger merger and acquisition strategies, we need constant evaluation and adjustment to the net neutrality policies. Otherwise, according to Moore's Law, the regulations will not keep up with the speed of development.

Finally, the research can benefit from expanding the scope of case studies to include a wider range of countries, particularly those with diverse economic and political systems, which can provide valuable insights into the global dynamics of net neutrality. For example, progressive European nations that uphold net neutrality laws, such as the Netherlands, Belgium, or Slovenia.

Conclusion and Recommendation

This paper provides a comparative analysis of net neutrality policies in Colombia, India, and the United States, revealing the complex interplay of legal frameworks, societal factors, and consequences for various stakeholders. While the net neutrality debates in the U.S., India, and Colombia share common threads, especially in terms of zero-rating practices, telecom companies' attempts to redefine the issue, and the role of civil society, the outcomes have been shaped by each country's unique digital landscape and the level of public engagement. The strong activism seen in the U.S. and India has led to significant policy changes, while in Colombia, the challenges of digital inclusion and the digital divide have limited public involvement. These diverse experiences underscore the critical need for policymakers to adopt a comprehensive approach to Internet governance. By addressing these issues, policymakers of the three countries mentioned in the case study section can help in creating a future where the internet remains a powerful tool for democratizing access to information, safeguarding freedom of expression, fostering innovation, and promoting social and economic progress for all through equal participation.

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